

STATIC AND DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF CHASSIS THROUGH FEA/FEM

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Abstract:

The static and dynamic analysis of the chassis plays an important role for designing of any type of goods carrier or passenger vehicle. Whole structure and also all type of loads whether pay loads or vehicle components load totally depends on chassis strength. So prior to any design chassis design is made. It is also used for supports all types of complicated loads coming from the road and pay loads. So, the strength and design of chassis play a big role in designing of any vehicle. A chassis of 4 wheels, has been studied and analyzed using HYPERMESH software package. Finite element analysis and dynamic analysis has been done with the help of software to study different loading cases and also vibration modes have been analyzed during the loading condition. Thus, results show stress , displacement and natural frequency of the chassis structure as well as under shock loading condition obtained from the chassis model.

Keywords: Static and Dynamic Analysis , Hypermesh , Stress , Displacement , Natural frequency

INTRODUCTION

Now a days increasing demands of chassis used for different vehicle for transportation or carrier vehicle has been increased not only on cost and weight and also on improved complete vehicle features. This results in increasing focus on optimization and modularization which together with large number of vehicle variants makes it necessary to use efficient analysis methods.

Finite element method/Finite element analysis has become an important part for development of vehicle chassis for development of many vehicle features. Chassis used for vehicle mounted on wheel upholds the loads above the ground for various purpose to transport the loads from one place to another.

While it is to difficult to quote a date of the invention of the finite element method, the method originated from the need to solve complex elasticity and structural analysis problems in civil and aeronautical engineering. It china, in the later 1950s and early 1960s , based on the computation of dam construction , K.Feng proposed a systematic numerical method for solving partial differential equations. The finite element method obtained its real impetus in the 1960s and 1970s by the developments of J.H. Argyris. A rigorous mathematical basis to the finite element method was provided in 1973 with the publication by Strang and Fix. A variety of specializations under the umbrella of the mechanical engineering discipline (such as aeronautical, biomechanical, and automotive industries) commonly use integrated FEM in design and development of their products.

In present work finite element model has been built up for 4 wheel either goods carrier or passenger vehicle , chassis in order to simulate the effect of different loads under different conditions. A static analysis with necessary boundary and loading condition have been applied on the model using HYPERMESH software and to evaluate the induced stresses and deformations on the chassis during the different loading conditions. Also dynamic(modal) analysis has been done on platform to obtained natural frequency of the system.

Thus the results obtained from analysis on the chassis is used to design the chassis more accurately and precisely and helpful to finalize the design without any destructive method. It was found that the results obtained from Hypermesh software is almost near the experimental values.

Finite element analysis of chassis

For the FE Analysis, it is necessary to create a solid model of chassis in order to create a FE model. In present work, load is acted to chassis at its positions under gravity loading. Loads are applied at their position under loading boundary condition to study the impact of loading in form of stress, displacement and frequency.

Mount aggregates Details :

S. No.	Mass (Kg)
Cabin Weight	165
Half Ton Crane	60
Primary Battery with Structure	350
Cylinder Structure	507
Auxiliary Battery with Structure	118
Pneumatic Control Structure	182
Total	1382

Model of Chassis

The chassis used in the form of step , parasolid in hypermesh software to obtained the hypermesh file. The material of chassis is steel(IS 2062:FE 410) with yield strength 250MPa and tensile strength of 410MPa. The properties of chassis are listed in below table.

Table: Properties of chassis material

Modulus of Elasticity E(Pa)	210x10 ⁹
Density(kg/m ³)	7800
Poisson ratio	0.3
Yield strength(MPa)	250
Ultimate tensile strength(MPa)	410

In elasto-static problem, each element forms a stiffness matrix, [K], relating forces [F] and displacements[u] at nodes. The size of the stiffness matrix is equal to the number of nodes per element multiplies by the number of freedom per nodes, as in the following

$$[F] = [K] [U]$$

In eigenvalue problem, the characteristic matrix is formed as

$$\{[K] - \omega^2 [M]\} [U] = 0$$

Where M is the mass matrix, ω^2 are eigenvalues, and u is the eigenvectors. In structural dynamics, the values are the natural frequencies and the vectors are mode shapes.

Loads and Boundary Conditions :

1. Chassis's mass is inclusive of all equipment.
2. Chassis with the mounted aggregates puts load on four vehicle wheel.
3. All the degrees of freedom at the four corners restrained.
4. g vertically downward acceleration is applied.

The meshed platform model is shown below figure 1.

Figure 1: Meshing or Discretization of Chassis model

Stress and Displacement developed after applying loads shown in figure 2 and 3 below.

Figure 2: Von Mises stress for most of the structure is below 104 MPa

Figure 3: Maximum Displacement of 1.5 mm at the crane loaded portion of the chassis.

Modal Analysis :

In this analysis different frequency modes has been obtained under loading Condition.

Figures 4 , 5 ,6 shown below are modal analysis for the chassis.

Figure 4: First Bending mode experienced by chassis at 44 Hz.

Figure 5: Second Bending mode experienced by chassis at 68 Hz.

Figure 6: First twisting mode experienced by chassis at 112 Hz.

Results and discussion :

The above results shown from figure 2 to 6 of stress , displacement and modal analysis of chassis after analysis. It can be seen that maximum Von Mises stress developed is 104MPa and displacement is 1.5mm. The first mode of frequency is about 44Hz and second mode of frequency is 68Hz in bending whereas in twisting it is 112Hz.

Conclusion:

We find that the stress and displacement obtained is under safe condition of chassis used. So, the structure for loading about 1.3 Ton is safe to use. Rest of safety depends on manufacturer used for it. Otherwise results obtained for the chassis is good enough for the manufacturer to used these values accordingly.

Future Scope :

1. To decrease the manufacturing cost by the use of FEM/FEA.
2. Analysis method is the non-destructive method for the design of structure over another method so can be used widely by the designer.

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